

27th January 2022

Ref. no. IRB/COHS/STD/06/Jan-2022

To,
Nada Alnuaimi
Reg. No: 2020MPT05
College of Health Sciences
Gulf Medical University
Ajman, UAE

Subject: Institutional Review Board Approval

Dear Student/s

Greetings from Gulf Medical University, Ajman.

This is to inform you that the Institutional Review Board has reviewed your research project titled "**Comparison of effectiveness of single exercise into pain program versus Shoulder Symptom Modification Procedure (SSMP) with early tendon loading, Heavy Slow Resistance exercise in patients with rotator cuff-related shoulder pain: a Randomised Controlled Trial**". The study has been approved. You are required to report to your supervisor / co-supervisor Dr. Ramprasad M, Associate Professor, College of Health Sciences, GMU.

The data collected by you shall be used only for the purpose of conducting the research study. Any information obtained in connection with the study should be treated as confidential. Any violation of these terms and conditions will be treated as personal/ academic misconduct that may warrant further action in this regard.

Best Regards

Prof. Salem Chouaib
Chairperson, Institutional Review Board